

Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System

Work Package 8

Procedures for CO₂ Fluxes Measurements with Portable Flux-Meters in Critical Zone Observatories (Bio-Geochemical Flux Laboratory, IGG-CNR)

Simona Gennaro¹, Angelica Parisi¹, Francesca Avogadro di Valdengo¹, Brunella Raco¹, Ilaria Baneschi¹, Antonello Provenzale¹, Mariasilvia Giamberini¹

¹ Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Geoscienze e Georisorse, Via Moruzzi, 1, 56124 Pisa, Italy.

ABSTRACT

This report updates the previous Italian version of the procedures for CO₂ fluxes measurements with portable flux-meters in Critical Zone Observatories (CZO) published in the CZO community of IGG-CNR on the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/records/7544045>). We present a full description of the procedures applied for the punctual measurements of CO₂ fluxes in grasslands. Specifically, procedures are referred to data acquired by portable flux-meters by the IGG-CNR personnel. Data are in general acquired during field campaigns aimed to measure CO₂ flux exchanges between soil, vegetation, and atmosphere at the IGG-CNR Critical Zone (CZ) observatories. Although these procedures are applied during field campaigns, sharing this information in the new-born Critical Zone Virtual Research Environment is essential in the spirit of creating shareable and FAIR data and results. In general, these procedures can be adapted to the measurements of other fluxes (e.g., CH₄, H₂O, and total VOC) and in other natural environments.

Keywords: Critical Zone; Virtual Research Environment; CO₂ Fluxes; IRGA; Flux chambers; Measurement Procedure

Contacts:

Simona Gennaro: simona.gennaro@igg.cnr.it

Mariasilvia Giamberini: mariasilvia.giamberini@igg.cnr.it

Cite as: Gennaro, S., Parisi, A., Avogadro Di Valdengo, F., Raco, B., Baneschi, I., Provenzale, A., Giamberini, M. (2024). Procedures for CO₂ Fluxes Measurements with Portable Flux-Meters in Critical Zone Observatories (Bio-Geochemical Flux Laboratory, IGG-CNR). CNR Internal Report.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14718968>

INDEX

1. Introduction	3
2. Portable Instruments Kit – Components and hints for use.....	4
3. Fieldwork: Use of Portable Flux-Meter and Accumulation Chambers for measuring CO ₂ fluxes at the soil- vegetation- atmosphere interface.....	12
4. Raw Data Processing	18
5. Conclusions and Future Perspectives	21
References	22
Acknowledgment.....	23

1. Introduction

The “Earth Critical Zone” (or “Critical Zone”) was defined for the first time by Ashley (1988) and represents the superficial layer (“skin”) of the Earth's crust, where all the processes that support the functioning of ecosystems, and life itself, take place.

This report describes the procedure applied by the team of the “Bio-Geochemical Flux Laboratory” of the Institute of Geosciences and Earth Resources of the CNR (IGG-CNR) for the measurements of CO₂ fluxes using portable flux-meters in the framework of Critical Zone (CZ) monitoring campaigns in alpine grasslands and arctic tundra. These procedures can be adapted to the measurements of other fluxes (e.g., CH₄, H₂O, and VOC) and to other environments. In general, fluxes measurement procedures are applied in specific CZ monitoring sites named “observatories” (hereafter named “CZOs”; e.g., CZO@Nivolet, CZO@Bayelva and CZO@Mt.Etna for alpine, arctic, and volcanic sites respectively).

This method allows to measure the Net Ecosystem Exchange (NEE, i.e. the total net flow resulting from the individual contributions of absorption and emissions of CO₂) and the Ecosystem Respiration (ER, i.e. the total of CO₂ emissions from the ecosystem into the atmosphere, composed by autotrophic respiration (by plants) and heterotrophic respiration (by soil micro-organisms). The Gross Primary Production (GPP) can therefore be obtained by the difference between NEE and ER, as follow: $GPP = NEE - ER$, where ER is always positive and NEE can be either positive or negative, depending on the prevailing process.

2. Portable Instruments Kit – Components and hints for use

The Bio-Geochemical Flux Laboratory (IGG-CNR, Pisa) is equipped with several instruments aimed to the measurements of gas fluxes at the interface between soil, vegetation, and atmosphere (named “flux-meters”, [Table 1](#)). They consist of distinct parts that have been engineered and assembled together.

The portable kit for flux measurements consists of a specific set of sensors and analysers coupled with an accumulation chamber and powered by batteries. The sensor for the measurement of CO₂ concentration (Infra-Red Gas Analyser, also known as IRGA) and the electronic components are enclosed in a robust case-backpack (identifiable as the yellow box in the [Fig. 1](#)) which can be easily transported during field campaigns.

Figure 1. The typical instrument configuration used for measuring CO₂ flux involves specific equipment and tools that enable accurate and reliable data collection. This setup is critical for accurately measuring CO₂ flux in various applications and scenarios (modified after Parisi et al., 2023).

ID (Sites of use)	Detectors	Probes for soil variables	Meteo station	Associated AC code
WS1615 (CZO@Bayelva, CZO@Nivolet)	LI-840 CO₂ IRGA (InfraRed Gas Analyser) CH₄ -TLD (<i>tunable laser diode</i>) VOC -PID (<i>Photo Ionization Detector</i>) H₂S -TOX	Thermometer Pt100 Volumetric Water Content (VWC) sensor Delta-T SM150T based on TDR (<i>Time Domain Reflectometry</i>) technology	Pyranometer DPA053 (serial nr. 21030296) Thermo-hygrometer DMA672.1	AC Artic or AC2102
WS1803 (CZO@Nivolet)	LI-850 CO₂/H₂O IRGA CH₄ -TLD VOC -PID H₂S -TOX	Thermometer Pt100 VWC sensor Delta-T SM150T	Pyranometer DPA053 (serial nr. BV1703163) Thermo-hygrometer DMA672.1 (serial nr. AW1704660)	AC2101
WS2005 (CZO@Mt.Etna)	LI-830 CO₂/H₂O IRGA CH₄ -TLD VOC -PID H₂S -TOX	Thermometer Pt100 VWC sensor Delta-T SM150T	Pyranometer Thermo-hygrometer (serial nr. SB2201)	AC2103
WS2101 (CZO@Bayelva)	LI-850 CO₂/H₂O IRGA	Thermometer Pt100 VWC sensor Delta-T SM150T	Pyranometer DPA053 Thermo-hygrometer DMA672.1	AC Artico2

Table 1. Flux-meters and accumulation chambers (AC) belong to IGG-CNR in Pisa. The flux-meters that can be used in Arctic sites (Bayelva, Ny-Ålesund) are equipped for measuring low fluxes in extreme environments and with transceiver radios with respect to the Norwegian Government's restrictions (see also the "Researchers' Guide" by the Ny-Ålesund Research Station Norway, online at: <https://nyalesundresearch.no/research-and-monitoring/researchers-guide/>). The characteristics of the soil probes and meteo station instruments are described further on in this document.

IRGA sensors and gas sampling

The InfraRed Gas Analysers (IRGA) are non-dispersive infrared sensor (or NDIR sensor) that measure the CO₂ and H₂O concentrations in the air sampled inside the accumulation chambers.

LICOR LI-840 or LI-850 infrared (IR) spectrometers are used as IRGAs (see Table 1 for details); they are connected to the accumulation chambers via thin rilsan tubes (two for each portable kit), one for incoming gas flow and the other for outgoing gas flow. "Gas in" and "gas out" rilsan tubes have the following dimensions: length: 1.8 m, internal diameter: 4 mm; external diameter 6 mm. The incoming gas flow (the sampling line) is protected by two filters that allow gases and water vapour to pass through, while blocking liquid water and dust particles. Specific characteristics of the filters are described in Table 2. The case also contains another filter for further protection from dust and a pump.

Hints for use:

Before starting the measurements, the flux-meters must reach the optimal operating temperature (≈ 50 °C). For this reason, they must be turned on at least 10-15 minutes before by using the On/Off button located on a panel on the outside of the yellow case.

Type of barrier	PTFE diameter (mm)	Pore size (µm)
PFTE membrane filter	50 mm	0.45 µm
PFTE membrane filter	25 mm	0.20 µm

Table 2. Specific characteristics of the two filters that “protect” the sampling line allowing gases and water vapour to pass through, while blocking liquid water and dust particles.

Flux accumulation chambers

The transparent polymethyl methacrylate cylindrical accumulation chambers (ac) represent the part of the “portable kit” aimed to collect air samples of the portion of the atmosphere where the CO₂ gas exchange occurs. Table 3 reports the dimensions of the various accumulation chambers used in IGG-CNR laboratories. The shape and dimension of the chambers can differ according to the specific applications, and a factor that must be considered is the height of the chamber, which determines the effective rate of CO₂ concentration variation. The lower the chamber height, the higher the sensitivity of measurements. A pressure sensor is installed inside the accumulation chambers. The atmospheric pressure in millibars is recorded using a digital barometer located in the upper part inside the accumulation chamber (e.g., AC2101, AC2102, AC2103). The final atmospheric pressure value is derived from the average of the values recorded at a frequency of 1 Hz during the flow measurement.

Inside the ac, the CO₂ concentration changes during the measurement time for the uptake of the CO₂ by the living vegetation through photosynthesis and/or the emission through respiration by autotrophic and heterotrophic organisms (plants and mainly soil microbial or fungal communities, respectively).

Air from the chamber “headspace” is then pumped at a constant flow rate (1 l/min and 3 l/min for Arctic flux-meters and for the others, respectively) into the IRGA (LI-COR Biosciences, Lincoln, NE, USA) through the (1.8 m long) rilsan tube pipe. The sample is then returned to the chamber. The return pipeline ends with a 40 cm long perforated rilsan tube placed around the lower diameter of the chamber, which guarantees good mixing of the air inside the chamber.

Hints for use:

All the accumulation chambers must be handled carefully to avoid scratches, which can affect flux measurements of Net Ecosystem Exchange (NEE). Each ac is coupled with a stainless-steel ring, which is inserted into the ground (for about 1-2 cm) at the sampling point, trying to maintain the site (as much as possible) undisturbed. The chamber is then placed on top of the ring. This procedure must be carefully done, to place the rim of the chamber correctly on the ring and to place the ring correctly on the soil to avoid atmospheric air contamination during measurements. When the ac is positioned on the ring, a closed system inside the chamber is created and the air space isolated is named “headspace”.

A soft cloth is used to cover the accumulation chambers, allowing to acquire data in dark conditions and measure the Ecosystem Respiration (ER and, thus, CO₂ uptake).

Accumulation chamber	Coupled FM	Production Year	Height (m)	Radius (m)	Surface (m ²)	Volume (m ³)	Note
AC2101	FM1803	2021	0.342	0.107	0.036	0.012 *	CZO@Nivolet
AC2102	FM1615	2021	0.342	0.107	0.036	0.012 *	CZO@Bayelva, CZO@Nivolet
AC2103	FM	2021	0.342	0.107	0.036	0.012 *	CZO@Mt.Etna
AC2307	FM2302	2023	0.342	0.107	0.036	0.012 *	
AC2409 §	FM2405	2024	0.100	0.021025	0.0661	0.00661	Specific for air-water interfaces (e.g., wetlands lakes, lagoons, marshes)
AC Artico	FM 1615	2019	0.097	0.145	0.6600185	0.006403795	CZO@Bayelva
AC Artico2	FM Artico	2021	0.097	0.145	0.6600185	0.006403795	CZO@Bayelva

*Table 3. Information and characteristics regarding the accumulation chambers (AC). “FM” stays for “flux-meter”. In general, the id used for identifying instruments used in a specific field campaign is referred to the flux-meter identification code. Calibration frequency: at the beginning and end of fieldwork seasons. * For volume values: the ring (2 cm) is included. § The AC2409 and the FM2405 are the last AC and FM that the Institute of Geosciences and Earth Resources – CNR (Pisa) acquired as part of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) (mission 4 component 2 - investment 3.1 - ITINERIS project) to upgrade the CZ laboratory facilities and to support the ITINERIS WP8 project - Activity 8.1 - VRE Critical Zone Services. In particular, this floating chamber will be devoted to the analysis of fluxes dynamics at the air-water interface.*

For each instrument kit, a portable meteorological station, provided with a thermo-hygrometer and a pyranometer, is also used (Figs. 1 and 2).

Meteo stations

Each flux-meter kit includes a meteorological station, made of a shielded thermo-hygrometer and a pyranometer (LSI LASTEM DMA672.1 and LSI LASTEM DPA053A, respectively; Fig. 2), mounted on a tripod. These instruments measure relative air humidity (Air-RH, %), air temperature (Air-T, °C) and solar radiance (SolarRad, W m⁻²) at 1.5 m above the ground (Table 4). The meteo station for the CZO@Bayelva observatory is equipped with its own datalogger due to the prohibition to use the Bluetooth connectivity.

Figure 2. Components of the portable meteorological station are a) a pyranometer (spectrally flat Class C), an b) anti-radiation screen and c) the thermo-hygrometer (photos by © LSI LASTEM).

Soil probes

Typical configuration of each kit includes probes for measuring soil temperature (Soil-T, °C) and soil volumetric water content (Soil-VWC, %), acquired at depths of approximately 10 and 5 cm, respectively. Soil-Temperature is measured using a Pt100 thermometer, while the VWC is measured using the Delta-T sensor SM150T (Fig. 3a). The SM150T is a high-quality and accurate device that can be used for instant soil moisture measurements. This sensor (Fig. 3a) consists of a two sensing stainless steel rods that are directly inserted into the soil. The power applied to the SM150T sharp rods creates an electromagnetic (EM, waveform) field which is transmitted into the soil. Soils are a mixture of minerals, gases, liquids and organic matter and, for this reason, their permittivity depends on the water content, which influences the induced field detected by the SM150T (Delta-T Devices Ltd, 2016). This results in a stable voltage output that represents a simple and sensitive measurement of soil moisture content (Delta-T Devices Ltd, 2016). Technical characteristics of sensors and probes are provided in Table 4.

Hints for use:

The disturbance of the soil is minimal with this sensor, but the two thin and sharp rods are very sensitive and breakable. More details are available in the paragraph dedicated to the description of detailed recommendations on the fieldwork ("[3. FIELDWORK: CRITICAL ZONE MONITORING USING PORTABLE FLUX-METERS AND THE ACCUMULATION CHAMBERS](#)"). The SM150T sensor is supplied by Delta-T Devices Ltd with two types of calibrations, for organic and mineral soils. However, it is also possible to calibrate the sensor for specific soil characteristics (Delta-T Devices Ltd, 2016). The Soil-T probe is a high-quality Platinum Resistance Thermometer (PRT) - Resistance Temperature Detector (RTD) and it is shown in Fig. 3b. The final values of Soil-T and Soil-VWC variables are obtained by averaging the values recorded with a frequency of 1 Hz during the flux measurements, excluding the initial values because of the acclimatization time for the instrumentation.

Figure 3. a) Soil-VWC probe (Delta-T SM150T). Warning: People must avoid touching the two sensing stainless steel rods. Best practice: People should always use the specific case to “protect” the thin pins. b) Probe for Soil-T made by a Platinum Resistance Thermometer (PTR, RS PRO).

Measured variables	Probes	Model; Producer	Measurement Range	Precision	Uncertainty	Principle / technology
Air-T	Thermo-hygrometer	DMA672.1; LSI LASTEM Srl	[-50 °C:100 °C]	0.1 °C (@0 °C)	0.2 °C	RTD Pt100
Air-RH			[0:100 %]	±1 % (@5:95 %)	2.0 %	capacitative
SolarRad	Pyranometer (spectrally flat Class C)	DPA053A; LSI LASTEM Srl	[0:2000 W m ⁻²]	±1 % (100:1000 W m ⁻²)	2.40 % [W m ⁻²]	
Soil-T	Probe for soil T made by a Platinum Resistance Thermometer	Pt100 Industrial Sensor Probe, Class B; RS PRO	[-50 °C:100 °C]	0.05 °C	0.055 °C	PRT - RTD Pt100
Soil-VWC	Soil Moisture Sensor (VWC)	SM150T; Delta-T Devices Ltd.	[0:100 %]	±3.0 % vol over 0 to 70 % vol and 0-60 °C	±3.0 % vol over 0 to 70 % vol and 0-60 °C	Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR)
Pressure	Digital barometer	MPL3115A2; NXP (This model is discontinued).	[500:1100 hPa]	±0.5 hPa	±2.5 hPa	Semi-conductors / Freescale

Table 4. Details and technical characteristics of the different probes and sensors.

Data recording

All sensors and the portable meteorological stations are connected to a handheld computer via Bluetooth connectivity (radio for the instrumental set-up for the Arctic) and provided with a GPS, for recording data from all sensors.

A software developed by WEST System srl and available for free on Google Play (the FluxManager2 app, latest update released on 28/08/2019) is devoted to data acquisition and allows to collect data from all sensors in a unique file, together with GPS coordinates.

The flux-meters used at the Ny Ålesund research base in Svalbard are equipped with transceiver radios to be connected with the Android device, because Bluetooth and Wi-Fi connectivity are not allowed (CZO@Bayelva, Ny-Ålesund, Arctic); For this set up, the synchronization of meteorological variables is performed at a later stage than field measurements (see in the [Table 1](#) the instruments with the label “Arctic”). Details on data acquisition are provided in the paragraph “[3. FIELDWORK: CRITICAL ZONE MONITORING USING PORTABLE FLUX-METERS AND THE ACCUMULATION CHAMBERS](#)”.

[Table 5](#) provides a detailed equipment checklist for conducting fluxes measurement during field campaigns aimed at monitoring the CZ. Teams of each field campaigns should carefully check and fill in all parts of the form. Each part of all equipment is identified with a label that refers to a specific flux-meter identification code (id).

After the field campaign season, all instruments are checked; a calibration is performed before and at the end of measurement campaigns (Giamberini et al., 2022). The Bio-Geochemical Flux Laboratory (IGG-CNR, Pisa) is also equipped with an instrument's calibration bench.

Equipment checklist for conducting fluxes measurement campaigns.

Field campaign information

Location of field campaign

Starting date (dd/mm/yyyy)

End date (dd/mm/yyyy)

Flux-meter

Responsible of the campaign

Email of the Responsible of the campaign

People involved in the field

Please, check the answer "Ok" or "NOT ok". If something is NOT ok, you should insert a specific note, contact the responsible for the next mission and send a brief report to igg-ecz-nivolet@igg.cnr.it.

List of equipment	ID / Code	Number	Equipment checklist BEFORE the campaign	Equipment checklist AFTER the campaign	Note
Box to transport the instruments	//				
Flux-meter					
Flux-meter - Battery charger					
Flux-meter – Carrier frame system					
Portable meteorological stations					
Portable meteorological stations - Pyranometer					
Portable meteorological stations - Thermo-hygrometer					
Portable meteorological stations - Battery charger					
Portable meteorological stations - Tripod					
Portable meteorological stations - Case					
Handheld device					
Handheld device - Battery charger					
Accumulation chamber					
Accumulation chamber - Battery charger					
Accumulation chamber - Soft polyester coverages					
Stainless-steel ring					
Soil-T probe Pt100					
Soil-VWC probe					
Soil-VWC probe – Cable					
Soil-VWC probe – Case					
Power strip for electrical sockets					
Logbook: Field campaign Notebook					

Table 5. Equipment checklist for conducting fluxes measurement campaigns. The equipment checklists (before and after the field campaign) must be compiled with the answers "Ok" or "NOT ok". If something is NOT ok, you should insert a specific note, contact the responsible for the next mission and send a brief report to igg-ecz-nivolet@igg.cnr.it.

3. Fieldwork: Use of Portable Flux-Meter and Accumulation Chambers for measuring CO₂ fluxes at the soil- vegetation- atmosphere interface

This paragraph describes the operative instructions to be implemented during fieldwork activities aimed at measuring CO₂ fluxes at the interface between soil, vegetation, and atmosphere:

- Turn on the fluxmeter. Ensure the fluxmeter is turned on sufficiently early to allow the analysers to reach operational temperature conditions, i.e. it is essential to wait about 10-15 minutes before starting measurements to allow the IRGA to reach the temperature of 51°C. The FluxManager2 app shows a warning if the sensor temperature is lower than 50°C.
- Turn on the meteorological station.
- Properly connect the tubing between the flow meter and the accumulation chamber, verifying that the tubes or rubber connections are not damaged. The inlet and outlet tubes are easily distinguishable, with the inlet featuring anti-particulate filters. Inspect the condition of any gaskets if present.
- Turn on the accumulation chamber sensors (if present).
- Turn on the handled device (e.g., the smartphone) by opening the FluxManager2 app and establish a Bluetooth (or radio) connection with the instrumentation. Verify the readings from each sensor. Check that all sensors are connected and are working correctly (i.e. values displayed make sense).
- If some of the sensors does not connect properly, use the button “scan” of the app and try again, then press “connect”.
- Position the stainless-steel ring on the soil, making sure that the ring perfectly adheres to the soil and no air passes between the lower edge of the ring and the soil.
- Position the soil probes, making sure that the temperature probe reaches 10 cm depth, and the Soil Moisture probe is at least 20 cm far from the temperature probe and the steel collar, to avoid interferences.
- Start the pump and let air flow in the flux chamber for cleaning it, at least 10 seconds or until the CO₂ concentration reading is constant.
- Carefully place the flux chamber over the collar and start recoding the CO₂ concentration values. The measurement should continue until enough CO₂ concentration values is acquired, i.e. until it is possible to perform a linear regression of the slope of the concentration vs time curve, with an R² value of at least 0,9. This should require between 60 and 90 seconds. The linear regression can be verified during the measurement by using the “flux manager” software.
- Record the environmental variables in the field logbook, including: day, time, site, fluxmeter, chamber, operator’s name, photographer, weather conditions (such as sunny or cloudy), air temperature, relative humidity, vegetation type cover, and any other pertinent additional information, plus CO₂ concentration slope in ppm/sec and its associated R² value. The notebook should summarize the values obtained at each measurement point and any relevant information for the subsequent data processing phase, in addition to the data recorded in the palmtop computer.

By following those detailed procedures and operational actions, you can ensure the success and reliability of your fieldwork activities; more tips on the best practices and recommendations that the operators involved in the fieldwork must consider are described here.

Fieldwork aimed to acquiring data on primary productivity and ecosystem respiration, particularly during the summer season, is an essential part of the CZ monitoring and should be organized in advance, at least sketchily since March for the summer season.

The logbook should report general information on the location, operator names, site name, date, timing, and weather (Table 6). During the field campaign, data on meteorological parameters and the height of the vegetation should also be noticed in the fieldwork notebook.

At least twenty (20) points must be measured for each site and, the typical measurement procedure includes two consecutive measurements for each point: the first must be performed using the transparent accumulation chamber (NEE), while the second is a measurement in dark condition (ER) by using with the same accumulation chamber shaded with a dark cover (Cannone et al., 2016; Magnani et al., 2020, 2022; Wohlfahrt et al., 2005). Consequently, for each site, a table with at least 40 points will be created, as shown in Table 6. During all the measurement campaigns and for each CZO/site, measurement replicates at different points within the same plot allow to capture the small-scale variability and thus to represent the spatial variability in those specific measurement plots. Magnani et al. (2020) verified that for the CZO@Nivolet a minimum of 20 measurement points is required to represent the spatial variability in those specific measurement plots.

Recording weather conditions (such as sunny, cloudy, partly cloudy, windy, rainy, snowy) is useful for interpreting the results of the data processing phase. For this reason, it is recommended to record measured values of environmental variables, including the environmental concentration of CO₂, air temperature, relative air humidity, atmospheric pressure, and solar radiation as well as any additional relevant information. Measurements are conducted at various times of the day, but typically from 10:00 in the morning to 18:00 in the afternoon (Pavelka et al., 2018). This implies that measures include different weather conditions and capture natural weather variability during time.

Logbook compilation form for each measurement site

Location of field campaign		Site name
Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Starting time (hh:mm, CEST)	End time (hh:mm, CEST)
Flux-meter	Types of Weather	
Accumulation Chamber	Type of Accumulation Chamber	
People involved in the field		
Photo by		
Notes:		

# number of points	CO ₂ Slope	R ²	Soil-T (°C)	Soil-VWC (%) 3 in & 1 out	Height of vegetation (cm)	Time of the pic	Air T	Air P	Note
#1 NEE									
#2 ER									
#3 NEE									
#4 ER									
#5 NEE									
#6 ER									
#7 NEE									
#8 ER									
#9 NEE									
#10 ER									
#11 NEE									
#12 ER									
#13 NEE									
#14 ER									
#15 NEE									
#16 ER									
#17 NEE									
#18 ER									
#19 NEE									
#20 ER									

#21 NEE									
#22 ER									
#23 NEE									
#24 ER									
#25 NEE									
#26 ER									
#27 NEE									
#28 ER									
#29 NEE									
#30 ER									
#31 NEE									
#32 ER									
#33 NEE									
#34 ER									
#35 NEE									
#36 ER									
#37 NEE									
#38 ER									
#39 NEE									
#40 ER									

Other notes:

Table 6. Logbook compilation form for each measurement site.

Soil-T (°C) and Soil-VWC (%) are measured (and noticed in the notebook) by positioning the sensors nearby the stainless-steel ring, but not-too-close to avoid interference among the instruments and the ring. For the Soil-VWC, three measurements are taken within the ring area to evaluate the soil moisture range. Then the probe is placed outside the ring, at a point where the measured value is within the range measured inside the ring. It is a best practice to position the Soil-VWC probe at least 20 cm far from both the Pt100 thermometer, the ring or rocks to avoid interference. Avoid touching the two rods with hands, because this could create measurement alterations (with a temporary offset of about -10 mV) for at least one hour.

When trying to insert the Soil-VWC probe into the soil for the presence of hard elements (e.g., stones, rocks, pebbles), the rods should not be forced into the soil to avoid damage to the sensor (Delta-T Devices Ltd, 2016).

After the Soil-T and Soil-VWC probes positioning, the operator should take a photo of the stainless-steel ring at nadir, to be used for image processing of vegetation status. Moreover, pictures can be useful for botanical specific observations. The operator should write in the fieldwork logbook the time (hh:mm) of each ring's picture (Fig. 5) and the name of the operator who took the pictures.

Figure 4. Photo showing the position of the ring. Photo taken during the fieldwork performed on 15/06/2023 at 15:18 in the Gran Paradiso Group (Western Alps, Italy; photo by S. Gennaro).

When measuring CO₂ fluxes, the CO₂ concentration inside a chamber over a specific time interval is recorded. Then, fluxes are calculated by interpolating the CO₂ concentration curve as a function of time. In general, fluxes from the atmosphere to the ecosystem (e.g., the absorption of CO₂ through photosynthesis) are represented with a negative sign by convention, while the fluxes from the ecosystem to the atmosphere (ER) are represented with positive sign. Therefore, the ER can have only positive values, while the NEE (which can include both absorption and emissions of CO₂) has a negative value when there is a net absorption by the ecosystem, while it is positive when there is a net emission. Fluxes units for the NEE and the ER are [molCO₂ m⁻² day⁻¹] or [μmolCO₂ m⁻² second⁻¹].

At each measurement point, the stainless-steel ring is inserted into the ground. Before and after each measurement, the entire apparatus (including the chamber, the tubes and the IRGA) should be ventilated leaving

the suction pump active until a normal-ambient CO₂ concentration is recorded again. The normal-ambient CO₂ concentration can have a value ranging between 400 and 460 ppm depending on the measurement site conditions. Then, the ac is positioned on the ring to isolate the air space named “headspace” and to create a closed system inside the chamber. The real-time measures are recorded with the frequency of 1 Hz and shown for each sensor in the app display. This app has an interface for managing the measurements, viewing, and saving the data.

The user must press the “Start” button to start the flux measurement and the display of the handled device will start to show a graph. The graph will show only one sensor at a time and the “Next” button, or the up/down volume button will allow to switch between the sensors values displayed. Regardless of whether the sensor is visible in the background or has tracking disabled, recording remains active for all sensors.

The CO₂ concentration inside the accumulation chamber is generally measured for approximately 90 seconds. CO₂ Slope and the R² calculated for each measurement point are displayed when a starting-point and an endpoint are positioned in the graph showing the trend of the CO₂ concentration (ppm) vs time. The first tap on the display will place a left limit marker and it should be placed at least after about 30 seconds from the beginning of the measurements. The second tap on the screen will place the right limit marker and, once both cursors are placed, the slope of the curve and the R² coefficient are shown on the top right of the screen.

At the end of each measurement, a raw data file (as text file, *.txt) containing the measured values is created in the internal memory of the handled device. During the saving process the operator should consider a standard way to name the data files and should record the type of chamber used.

The default names (West System Srl, 2012)) of each file contain at least the following information (in this order): site name and information, the point number (this is referred to the number of replications performed on that specific site), date (ddmmyyyy) and time (hhmmss). The underscore symbol (“_”) is used to separate the different information.

At the end of every field campaign, the operator must download all the *.txt files generated for all the points measured in all the measurement sites into a pc by using a cable to connect the two device and opening the memory of the handled device as a normal folder. The Bio-Geochemical Flux Laboratory (IGG-CNR, Pisa) uses a specific IGG-CNR internal server to store a copy of all the raw data. The creation, in the working directory, of a folder named considering the measurement site and date (yyymmdd) is necessary for correctly storing the data. Photos must be renamed as follow: yyymmdd_SITE_#NEE -#ER (e.g., 20230614_GNE_27-28 for the photograph of the area inside the ring taken for the measurements of flux identified with the numbers 27 and 28 on the field-notebook).

4. Raw Data Processing

Raw data, collected in the field using the FluxManager2 app (saved as *.txt files), are reviewed and processed using the FluxRevision software (West Systems Srl; available online at the link: <https://www.westsystems.com/instruments/download/>), developed to run on Microsoft operating system (os) and allowing to quickly process a large number of files.

Here we report an example of data processing of data collected in the framework of the field campaign in the Lauson proglacial area, that was carried out in August 2023 (during two days of field work). Data were acquired along an altitudinal profile along the deglaciation transect.

Measured data were:

Date, time

Latitude, Longitude

CO₂ concentration vs time

Air Temperature

Air relative humidity

Solar Irradiance

Soil Volumetric Water Content

Soil temperature.

The user must ensure to save a backup of the raw data before starting with the processing phase.

A good practice consists in downloading the files related to the flux measurements on the PC and to proceed organizing the files into different folders; each folder should contain all the raw data related to a complete set of measurements per site and per day.

The calculation of the slope of the best linear interpolation of the CO₂ concentration vs time is done using a specific software called FluxRevision (v. 4.11, West System Srl).

Opening FluxRevision, the user selects the working directory (folder) where the .txt files of the measurements are stored. In this example, the user selects the folder “Lauson1846_09092023” (Fig. 6a). This allows to upload a “Measure List” (Fig. 6b) containing all the points measured in the specific site and day selected.

Figure 5. Flux Revision panel where a folder system is showed (a) and the personnel can select a specific file. The panel b) shows the “Measure List” on Flux Revision.

If environmental variables are missing in some files, the following pop-up window will appear on the screen (Fig. 7).

Figure 6. Pop-up window that appears on the screen if some raw data does not contain data on environmental variables (i.e., temperature and pressure). It is possible to indicate P and T to be replaced in case of missing data. Leaving as suggested by the software, FluxRevision will replace the missing data with P = 1013 mBar and T = 20 °C. A good practice is to choose unlikely values of P and T (e.g., P = 0 mBar and T = 50 °C), so that it is easier to identify missing environmental data in a subsequent data “cleaning & filling” phase. If “Apply to all analysis” is checked, the environmental parameters of all measurements will be overwritten with the values indicated in this step.

The user can choose several methods for interpolating the gas concentration vs. time curve for obtaining the best regression curve (Fig. 8 **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**) that allows to calculate the gas flux.

When all the interpolation curves have been selected for the specific dataset, and the relative slopes have been calculated, it is possible to extract a report (a chart) where all the measured parameters for the specific day/site are listed.

Figure 7. On the left: theoretical gas concentration vs. time curve (ppm s^{-1} ; West System Srl, 2012). On the right: FluxRevision screen that displays the linear interpolation interval manually selected by the user.

5. Conclusions and Remarks

Procedures and useful suggestions for field campaign are summarized in this report. It includes a brief descriptions of the main instruments that are used by the CNR-IGG team involved in the CZ research.

It is essential to use standardized procedures and share knowledge learned in the field to create FAIR data and results.

The selection of the sampling sites as well as the procedures used for data acquisition in the field are fundamental. Therefore, this collection of operative procedures must be shared with the community of the Critical Zone Virtual Research Environment (CZ VRE). The CZ VRE represents one of the Virtual Research Environments (VREs) created in the framework of the ITINERIS PNRR Project. The VREs represent spaces created to promote collaboration and cooperative work. The ITINERIS project aims to develop an overall hub of Italian Research Infrastructures (RIs) in the geo-scientific and environmental fields by creating thematic VREs (e.g., Critical Zone VRE; Isotope VRE). VREs are based on the D4Science infrastructure, which improves the effectiveness of the Open Science approach – based on transparency, inclusion, research integrity, collaboration, and cooperative work – through the development of these eScience facilities. In this framework, sharing information on field data acquisition methods and tips for successful field campaigns can contribute to the development of a collaborative environment.

References

- Ashley, G.M. (1998). *Where are we headed? "Soft" rock research into the new millennium*. Geological Society of America Abstract/Program, vol. 30. p. A-148.
- Brantley, S. L., McDowell, W. H., Dietrich, W. E., White, T. S., Kumar, P., Anderson, S. P., Chorover, J., Ann Lohse, K., Bales, R. C., Richter, D. D., Grant, G., & Gaillardet, J. (2017). *Designing a network of critical zone observatories to explore the living skin of the terrestrial Earth*. *Earth Surface Dynamics*, 5(4), 841–860. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esurf-5-841-2017>
- Cannone, N., Augusti, A., Malfasi, F., Palozzi, E., Calfapietra, C., & Brugnoli, E. (2016). *The interaction of biotic and abiotic factors at multiple spatial scales affects the variability of CO₂ fluxes in polar environments*. *Polar Biology*, 39 (9), 1581–1596. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-015-1883-9>
- Delta-T Devices Ltd (2016). *User Manual for the SM150T Soil Moisture Sensor*. User Manual Version: SM150T-UM-0.f Nov 2016.
- Giamberini, M., Parisi, A., Avogadro di Valdengo, F., Baneschi, I., & Raco, B. (2022). *Procedura di laboratorio - Calibrazione flussimetro portatile*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6638556>
- LSI LASTEM (2013). LSI LASTEM M-Log – User’s manual (INSTUM_00720_en). Update 19/12/2013.
- Magnani, M., Baneschi, I., Giamberini, M., Mosca, P., Raco, B., & Provenzale, A. (2020). *Drivers of carbon fluxes in Alpine tundra: a comparison of three empirical model approaches*. *Science of the Total Environment*, 732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139139>
- Magnani, M., Baneschi, I., Giamberini, M., Raco, B., & Provenzale, A. (2022). *Microscale drivers of summer CO₂ fluxes in the Svalbard High Arctic tundra*. *Scientific Reports*, 12 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-04728-0>
- Parisi, A., Giamberini, M., Avogadro di Valdengo, F., Raco, B., Baneschi, I., Lelli, M. (2023). *Procedura di misura - MONITORAGGIO DELLA ZONA CRITICA - MISURE DI FLUSSI DI CO₂ CON FLUSSIMETRO PORTATILE*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7544045>
- Pavelka, M., Acosta, M., Kiese, R., Altimir, N., Brümmer, C., Crill, P., Darenova, E., Fuß, R., Gielen, B., Graf, A., Klemetsson, L., Lohila, A., Longdoz, B., Lindroth, A., Nilsson, M., Jiménez, SM, Merbold, L., Montagnani, L., Peichl, M., ... Kutsch, W. (2018). *Standardization of chamber technique for CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ fluxes measurements from terrestrial ecosystems*. *International Agrophysics*, 32 (4), 569–587. <https://doi.org/10.1515/intag-2017-0045>
- West System Srl (2012). *Portable diffuse flux meter with LI-COR CO₂ detector*. Handbook – Release 8.2 September 2012.
- Wohlfahrt, G., Anfang, C., Bahn, M., Haslwanter, A., Newsely, C., Schmitt, M., Drösler, M., Pfadenhauer, J., & Cernusca, A. (2005). *Quantifying nighttime ecosystem respiration of a meadow using eddy covariance, chambers and modeling*. *Agricultural and Forestry Meteorology*, 128 (3–4), 141–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2004.11.003>

Acknowledgment

The volume/publication has been funded by EU - Next Generation EU - PNRR - Mission 4 “Education and Research” - Component 2 “From research to business” - Investment 3.1 “Fund for the realisation of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures” - Project ITINERIS Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System - IR0000032 - CUP B53C22002150006.